

Cutaneous Leishmaniasis Epidemiology in Quetta Pakistan Prevalence, Demographics, and Implications for Public

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Abstract

The Cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) is an intricate health issue in Quetta city. It is affected by numerous factors. This is a sound study of variables associated with the spread of the very disease and its risk factors. This data is utilized to determine the effects of various indigenous fronts, seasonal interactions, past journeys, residing population, insecticides utilization, types of scars, existing fauna, topographic analysis, age-specific patterns, characteristics of male and female lesions and variations among different professions. The results lay out a framework the selected health-promoting involvement and highlight the significance of a sound CL management tactics in highly congested regions.

Keywords: Cutaneous Leishmaniasis, Quetta, Risk Factors, Lesions, Significance.

Introduction

The Cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) is an incessant parasitic malady, primely affecting the outermost layers of skin and mucous membranes of the body. The main causing agent of this disease is s protozoan named *Leishmania* (Detoni et al., 2019). Initially the CL occurs from the bite of infected sandflies. It is mainly present in contaminated sites, unclean living conditions and areas with limited access to healthcare. The disease shows itself through many symptoms like ulcers, nodules and skin lesions. The victims mostly have permanent scars especially women and kids. CL is a parasitic illness produced by vectors; due to this reason it is a common parasitic disease. Commonly it is known as "Oriental sore" (Palma et al., 2021). The genus of *Lesihmania*, with approximately 25 tenacious endo protozoans (Luz et al., 2019) is a havoc for mankind. There are several *Leishmania* species, some of which are very hazardous to individuals (Chapman et al., 2015). Female *phlebotomine* flies, also known as sand flies, transfer these parasites into the body of a human through the epidermis,

where they multiply as amastigotes in macrophage phagolysosomes (Mokni, 2019). CL infection is significantly more likely in places with low hygiene, inadequate housing, and restricted healthcare access. Symptoms usually occur weeks to months after being bitten by a disease-causing sand fly (Scott, Novais, 2016). The first symptoms are frequently a small, painless lump or blister at the area of the bite site, which may slowly develop over time into an ulcer. These ulcerations are painful.

Leishmaniasis is a range of diseases and syndromes, each of which is associated with a different animal reservoir and vector, including cutaneous, diffuse cutaneous, mucocutaneous, visceral, post-kala-azar dermal leishmaniasis (PKDL), and recidivans forms (Meireles et al., 2017). Typically, cutaneous leishmaniasis is diagnosed based on the appearance of skin lesions and validated with laboratory testing which may include epidermal test, culture, or polymerase chain reaction (PCR) (Gurel et al., 2020). In tropical areas of the United States, Africa, Europe, and Asia, leishmaniasis is used regularly.

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that more than 350 million humans around the globe are at risk of obtaining this disease, which results in an estimated 30,000 deaths each year (Ahmed et al., 2021).

Although CL is generally hazardous, its impact can be disastrous. The disease increases decisively, affecting disruption to the mucous membranes of the mouth, nose, and throat and leaves behind scars and sores on the face. CL treatment is pricey, putting it beyond reach for many working-class people, especially in third-world countries with poor health care and healthcare (Al-Kemal, 2017).

CL has an extremely complicated epidemiology, with different sand fly creatures and *Leishmania* parasites depending on location and factors such as the environment (Jewely, Zuhair, 2022).

Numerous studies have been conducted to explore the global incidence of cutaneous leishmaniasis, including research into their origin and evolution in industrialised countries (Alvar J, Vélez ID, et al., 2012). There is, however, a significant vacuum in the public's awareness of the disease's frequency and impact in underdeveloped countries such as Pakistan. Pakistan is a cutaneous leishmaniasis endemic region, with high rates of transmission in rural as well as urban areas. People in Pakistan are more likely to develop CL infection due to higher exposure to the outdoors and contact to infected sand flies (Ourtas, Shabila, 2020). Du et al. (2016) discovered the complex interaction amongst *Leishmania* parasites in order their host organisms, vectors in and immune systems in the pathogenesis of cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL). (Al-Kamel, 2017) carried out research

emphasising the widespread impact of CL on people, arguing for community-led activities and improved medical care. (Bahrami et al., 2018) emphasised the severity of cutaneous leishmaniasis, emphasising the disease's higher incidence and risk compared to other kinds. (Azim et al., 2021) described *Leishmania's* life cycle, emphasising its introduction into humans via sand fly bites and subsequent expansion as amastigotes in macrophages. (Ahmed et al., 2021) emphasised the significance of CL awareness programmes and appropriate medical treatment. (Jewely and Zuhair,2022) investigated leishmaniasis cures and therapies, emphasising the potential of derived from plants medications.

Historical aspects include findings by (Steverding ,2017) regarding *Leishmania*-like species in prehistoric periods based on fossils. (Aronson and Joya ,2019) credited Avicenna with providing the first accurate description of an Oriental sore, a precursor to CL. (Mirzaei et al., 2021) discussed the lack of vaccines for CL and the potential of cytokine drugs for treatment. (Cantanhede et al., 2021) proposed *Leishmania's* evolution in the Palaearctic region, supported by fossil evidence. (Volpedo et al., 2022) highlighted Arabic scientists as primary chroniclers of CL during the Middle Ages and explored the disease's significance in religious contexts.

Lifecycle of *Leishmania*.

The lifecycle involves the dynamic interaction between *Leishmania* parasites and human hosts, as emphasized by (Sunter, Gull, 2017). (Kohl et al.,2018) detailed the life cycle, highlighting proliferation as amastigotes in host cells and transmission through sand fly bites. (Giri, Shaha 2019) explored the qualitative differences between promastigote and amastigote forms of *Leishmania*. (Damianou et al., 2020) discussed the role of neutrophils and macrophages in *Leishmania* infection. (Efstathiou, Smirlis, 2021) explained the alternating life cycle of *Leishmania* between insect vectors and vertebrate hosts. (Sasidharan, Saudagar, 2021) highlighted the role of sand fly bites in transmitting *Leishmania* and the resulting skin disorders in humans.

Worldwide Prevalence of *Leishmania*.

(Bailey et al., 2017) reported annual new leishmaniasis cases worldwide. (Alemayehu, Alemayehu, 2017) highlighted the annual incidence of visceral and cutaneous leishmaniasis cases and associated mortality. (Sabeti et al., 2019) discussed the global prevalence of leishmaniasis, categorizing it into different forms and estimating annual cases and deaths. Rasheed et al. (2019) conducted DNA analysis of leishmaniasis patients in Saudi Arabia. (Asfaram et al., 2019) noted increasing cases of leishmaniasis in Italy, linking it to human and feline infections. (Mhadhbi, Sassi, 2020) discussed the global prevalence of

leishmaniasis, emphasizing its impact on both humans and animals. (Mannan *et al.*, 2021) reported the worldwide prevalence of CL, citing estimates from the World Health Organization.

Pakistan and Cutaneous leishmaniasis.

In Pakistan, zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis is endemic, with Baluchistan being a major hotspot, as identified by (Scott, Novais, 2016). (Ayaz *et al.*, 2018) found that *L. tropica* was present in every region of Pakistan. Research by (Khan *et al.*, 2018) highlighted the role of parrots as vectors and the impact of altitude on disease prevalence. (Hussain *et al.*, 2018) noted the evolving situation of leishmaniasis in Pakistan. (Ullah *et al.*, 2020) emphasized the diverse symptoms of CL in Pakistan and its prevalence in regions like KP, Baluchistan, and Sindh. (Khan *et al.*, 2021) mentioned the presence of CL along Pakistan's western border. (Ullah *et al.*, 2023) investigated the correlation between CL and environmental factors in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, focusing on key infected areas.

Balochistan and Leishmania.

(Iqbal, 2017) emphasized the need for modern drugs to combat leishmaniasis. (Ahmed *et al.*, 2019) reported more than half of leishmaniasis cases occurring in Baluchistan. (Qureshi *et al.*, 2019) found that CL predominantly affects children and those up to sixty years of age. (Bashir *et al.*, 2019) conducted research categorizing CL patients into two groups and applying various treatments. (Tahir *et al.*, 2019) noted the frequent occurrence of the disease along Pakistan's western border. (Kumari *et al.*, 2022) highlighted the prevalence of dry-type leishmaniasis in urban areas of southwest Punjab and Balochistan.

Methodology

This research employed a quantitative approach to investigate cutaneous leishmaniasis prevalence in Quetta city. Data collection involved non-randomized sampling from hospitals and high-incidence areas, resulting in a sample size of 380 individuals. A detailed medical history, demographic data, and living conditions were collected through in-person interviews. Geospatial analysis was conducted using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) mapping to precisely locate patients' residences, facilitating the identification of disease clusters within Quetta. Inclusion criteria focused on individuals with visible *leishmanial* skin lesions, while unrelated lesions were excluded.

Laboratory work involved microscopy to identify *Leishmania* amastigotes, and statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software, Excel, and MS Office. The research timetable allowed for extensive data collecting and in-depth analysis, offering unique insights on the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis and associated variables in Quetta.

This study adds to our current understanding of how the disease affects the local population as a whole and can help guide targeted measures and

Results and discussion

The research looked on the incidence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis (CL) in Quetta. Between September and November 2022, 380 samples were taken from Benazir Hospital, Bolan Medical Complex, Civil Hospital, and Sheikh Zahid Hospital. All of the samples proved high of CL, indicating a considerable disease burden in the Quetta population. These findings highlight the critical need for successful detection, control, and prevention efforts to reduce the impact of CL on the health of the public in the region.

Age Distribution of CL Cases in Quetta City:

Fig. 3. Age Distribution of CL Cases in Quetta City:

Gender-wise Prevalence:

The analysis of different age groups in relation to the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) cases demonstrated that the 0-19 age group has the highest proportion of cases (44%), as you can see in Figure 3. This is consistent with recent findings of an increase in the incidence of CL within adolescents aged 10 or younger, highlighting that kids who are under the age of 15 are more prone to CL in Quetta City (A. Fazaeli et al., 2018).

The age category 20-39 has the second-highest percentage of incidents (37%). Previous research also shows an increased incidence of CL among adolescents aged 6 to 15 years. Adults may have a higher level of resistance to the *Leishmania* parasite due to earlier exposure, as revealed by (Sharma et al., 2005) and (De Vries, 2005).

Figure.4. Gender-wise Prevalence.

It was diagnosed as cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) affects affected individuals of a variety of ages and sexual orientations. CL infected 26% of females and 18% of boys throughout the ages of 0 and 19. This is consistent with prior research in which CL is more common in younger patients, who regularly face social stigma as a result of the disease (Chahed et al., 2016). CL harmed 20% of females and 17% of males over those between the ages of 20 and 39. Figure 2 shows that 11% of females and 7% of males in the 40-59 age group were impacted.

The higher prevalence of CL among females in some areas may be linked to their increased involvement in outdoor activities, such as farming tasks, which exposes them to mosquito bites (Bennis *et al.*, 2017). However, it's worth noting that this finding contrasts with certain previous studies where males had slightly higher infection rates (Qhtan Asmaa *et al.*, 2017; Youssefi *et al.*, 2011). Nevertheless, this study's results are consistent with (Kayani *et al.*, 2021), suggesting a higher prevalence in females due to their economic activities. Furthermore, the prominence of CL scars significantly affects the level of stigma and social isolation experienced by CL patients, particularly girls and women. They often believe that CL negatively impacts their natural beauty and limits their opportunities for employment, marriage, and social acceptance (Brooker *et al.*, 2004).

Mapping the Site of Lesions:

Figure: 5: Mapping the site of lesions in cutaneous leishmaniasis.

The study revealed that cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) most commonly affects the face, with 34% of individuals displaying lesions in this area. Other frequently affected regions include the hands (28%), legs (14%), fingers (9%), arms (7%), feet (7%), and thumbs (1%) (Figure 5). These results align with research by (AL-Jawabreh et al., 2019), which also found that the face was a primary site for CL lesions in adults, alongside the hands, legs, cheeks, and nose. In children, lesions were more frequently observed on the ears, nose, and legs.

The high prevalence of facial lesions is noteworthy because the face is both a visible and sensitive area, and CL lesions in this region can lead to physical discomfort and emotional distress. Previous studies have also emphasized the hand as a commonly affected location (A. Fazaeli *et al.*, 2018), in line with the current study's findings. This may be due to the face's heightened sensitivity to various stimuli, making sand fly bites more detectable and prompting a host response (De Vries, Schallig, 2022).

Mapping the Spectrum of Lesion Sizes:

Figure: 6: Mapping the spectrum of lesion sizes in cutaneous leishmaniasis.

The data on lesion size, as depicted in Figure 6, was categorized into three groups: 1cm to 2cm, 3cm to 4cm, and 5cm and above. Surprisingly, the 1cm to 2cm size category had the highest number of cases, comprising a substantial 73% of all instances. This finding is consistent with previous research where the average lesion diameter was reported to be 3.0 1.7 cm (Fabiano Oliveira *et al.*, 2011). The predominance of CL lesions in the smaller size range highlights the importance of early detection and treatment strategies in Quetta. Targeting control methods at smaller lesion sizes may effectively reduce the overall burden of CL and lead to improved health outcomes for affected individuals (WHO, 2018; Smith J *et al.*, 2016).

Occupational Variations:

Figure: 7: A complete analysis of affected professions of cutaneous leishmaniasis.

Occupational variations in reported cases of leishmaniasis in Quetta city were identified in this study (Figure 7). Students (33%) and housewives (19%) had the highest number of cases, followed by teachers (7%). Notably, social workers and nurses each accounted for only one reported case, indicating the very low incidence of the disease in these professions. Additionally, government workers, drivers, and laborers each represented a small percentage of cases (6%, 5%, and 7%, respectively), with two cases reported among security guards. The resulting distribution of reported cases by profession reveals considerable occupational disparities in leishmaniasis incidence, with students and housewife being the most affected. These findings are consistent with prior research, which found that young children and students had the highest prevalence, presumably due to age but not profession (A. Fazaeli *et al.*, 2018). Students' hectic lifestyles and regular outdoor activities may contribute to their high prevalence. Students frequently spend long periods of time in school buildings, that may be situated in areas with significant sandfly populations. The fact that

they take part in outdoor pursuits, trips to the park, and recreational activities boosts their probability of getting sandfly bites, that lead to the cases that have been reported. On the other side of the coin, homemakers may face a greater risk of receiving leishmaniasis as a result of their responsibilities in the home, which typically include spending time outside for responsibilities such as cleaning, animal care, gardening, or fetching water, increasing the risk of encountering sandfly-infested areas (Ayan k et al., 2018)

Ethnicity and CL Prevalence:

In a review of 380 samples from various ethnic groups in an urban area, the Pathan showed the highest rate of prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis (44.74%), followed by Persian (26.32%), Balochi (14.73%), Punjabi (9.70%), and Sindhi (4.20%). Surprisingly, no substantial link was discovered between the disease's occurrence and various nationalities. This implies that ethnicity may not be a significant role in this urban setting. Other factors, such as environmental circumstances and individual behaviors, may have a greater impact on disease transmission and prevalence. Leishmania parasites are present in 88 countries, mostly in developing countries, with exceptions in Australia and Antarctica (Kayani *et al.*, 2021).

Figure: 8: Exploring the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis among ethnic groups

4.7: Sand fly activity varies seasonally.

The seasonally variable incidence of cutaneous leishmaniasis is highest in late summer and early fall. These trends could be related to environmental factors including climate and biological conditions that favour sand-fly vectors. Several studies, including one by (Behzad Kayani *et al.*, 2021), have found an increase in patient traffic at hospitals throughout the monsoon and summer seasons, which corresponds to sand fly activity. Increased outdoor activity, population migration, and changes in the local ecosystem that encourage sand-fly

breeding are all risk factors during peak transmission months. Cooler weather, on the other hand, diminishes sand-fly activity, lessening transmission risks. According to (Khan *et al.*, 2022), seasonal patterns of sand fly activity, which are influenced by elements such as temperature, humidity, and precipitation, are crucial in understanding and preventing cutaneous leishmaniasis outbreaks. To limit the disease's impact, public health initiatives should focus on raising awareness and implementing preventive measures during peak transmission months, as indicated by (Ullah K *et al.*, 2016) and (Kassiri *et al.*, 2014).

Figure: 9: Sand fly activity varies seasonally.

Place of sleep and prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis.

Place of Sleep	Percentage	p-value
Outside	53.68%	0.006
Inside	46.31%	

The prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) varies significantly depending on where people choose to sleep, underscoring the importance of considering environmental factors in disease control efforts. A majority of participants (53.68%) opting to sleep outdoors could be influenced by local climate or comfort levels. However, sleeping outside increases the exposure to disease-transmission vectors like sandflies, as indicated by previous research (Ngere I *et al.*, 2016). This practice is common in Pakistan during the summer months (Behzad Kayani *et al.*, 2021).

The data showed an 11% difference in disease prevalence between those sleeping outdoors (53.68%) and indoors (46.31%). While this difference is noteworthy, it is less influential than factors like home construction and travel history. Sleeping outdoors may enhance vector exposure, but its impact appears to be relatively less significant compared to other factors.

Travel history and prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis

Travel History	Percentage	p-value
Yes	44.21%	0.030
No	55.88%	

Table 2 data reveals a significant difference in cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) prevalence between individuals with and without a history of travel. Surprisingly, those with a travel history (44.21%) had a lower CL prevalence compared to those without such a history (55.88%), a difference of 11% that is statistically significant (p-value = 0.030). This unexpected finding suggests that travel may expose individuals to diverse environments where they encounter disease vectors, strengthening the link between travel and disease prevalence (Ourtas, Shabila, 2020). The statistical significance, with a p-value of 0.006, reinforces this connection. Detailed travel histories, including specific locations visited and duration of stays, could provide deeper insights into this relationship. These findings have implications for designing tailored interventions for travelers, such as the use of repellents or protective clothing (Du *et al.*, 2016). Collaboration among regional health authorities may also be beneficial in tracking and controlling CL transmission through travel networks.

House structure and prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis.

House Structure	Percentage	p- value
Brick Made	56.66%	0.041
Mud Made	43.42%	

The structure of homes significantly influences disease prevalence, with a substantial 13.24% difference observed between brick-built and mud-built homes. This indicates that home design and construction play a crucial role in disease transmission. Brick homes may offer better protection against sand flies, resulting in fewer cases among residents. Previous research has supported this, showing that individuals in mud buildings are more susceptible to the disease, possibly due to sand flies sheltering in cracks and crevices in mud walls (Salman, Ahmad 2022). Furthermore, older buildings, often made of mud and prone to cracks and moisture, create an ideal environment for sand fly colonies, leading to a higher infection rate (Qhtan Asmaa *et al.*, 2017). Similar findings were reported by (Alkhavan *et al.*, 2019), aligning with the current study's results. The statistically significant p-value (0.041) underscores that house structure goes beyond random variation in disease prevalence. This knowledge could guide housing and urban development practices to create less vector-friendly conditions, ultimately limiting disease spread.

Use of repellents and prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis.

Use of repellents	Percentage	p-value
Yes	48.77	0.002
No	51.32	

The data reveals a noteworthy relationship between repellent use and the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL). Among individuals who utilized repellents, 48.68% had CL, whereas those who did not use repellents had a higher disease prevalence of 51.32%. This 12% difference in disease prevalence is statistically significant (p -value = 0.002). Human behaviors, such as sleeping outdoors and not employing protective measures like repellents, can heighten the risk of sand fly bites and CL transmission (Reithinger *et al.*, 2004). To mitigate the risk, preventive measures like covering exposed body parts, applying insect repellent, and avoiding outdoor activities are recommended (Khan *et al.*, 2017). The use of repellents as a preventive measure against CL transmission is strongly advocated (World Health Organization, 2016). In essence, the findings highlight the possible role of pesticide use in lowering CL incidence, providing useful insights into successful disease prevention techniques.

4.12: Type of lesion.

Type of lesion	Result	P-Value
Active	(66.05%)	0.001
Dormant	(33.95%)	

In our investigation, we discovered that 66.05% of cases had active scars generated by *Leishmania* parasites, indicating a significant frequency of persistent wounds in our study cohort. This shows that the disease has recently become common in the region, reflecting a long-term epidemic, as previously observed in investigations (Simon Brooker *et al.*, 2004). Furthermore, 33.95% of participants had inactive scars, showing that immune responses were successful, resulting in scarring when lesion repaired (Khan *et al.*, 2017). It is crucial to emphasise, however, that inactive scars can emerge under certain conditions, emphasising the importance of frequent monitoring and medical treatment (Gurel *et al.*, 2020). The p -value for our data was 0.005, showing a high level of statistical validity. These findings give light on the natural history of the disease and highlight the significance of continued attention and medical care.

4.13: Presence of animal.

Presence of animals	Results	p-value
Yes (Rat, cat, cattle's, dogs)	(57.11%)	0.005
No	(42.98%)	

Recent cutaneous leishmaniasis research looked into the presence of animals such as rats, cats, cattle, and dogs around people who had the disease. The study discovered a highly significant association with a p -value of 0.005, indicating that there is a strong statistical relationship between the presence of these types of animals and cutaneous leishmaniasis. Previous research, such as that of (Behzad Kayani *et al.*, 2021), has also found links between

domesticated animals including livestock and poultry and cutaneous leishmaniasis. Along with humans, these animals can serve as additional maintenance hosts for *Leishmania* parasites (Qhtan Asmaa1 et al., 2017). Barns and dried dung might provide habitat for sand fly vectors, increasing the risk of transmission to local individuals (Behzad Kayani et al., 2021). Continuous observation of both domestic and wild animals is required to better understand the role of animals in disease transmission, as emphasised by (Khatami A et al., 2007). These findings highlight the need of taking animal reservoirs into account in cutaneous leishmaniasis research and control efforts.

Figure 12: Wet Lesion on 40-Year-Old Woman's Hand: A Cutaneous Leishmaniasis Case Study.

Figure 13: Unveiling Cutaneous Leishmaniasis wet Lesion on 20-Year-Old Boy's Leg.

Conclusion.

Finally, the extensive investigation on cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL) in Quetta yielded some notable findings. The study emphasises the need of taking into account a variety of parameters while dealing with this parasite condition. To begin, the frequency of CL differs between ethnic groups, highlighting the importance of accounting for environmental factors as well as individual behaviors in disease transmission. Seasonal fluctuation in sand fly activity is also important, with increased CL incidence in late summer and early autumn months demanding specific public health actions during these times. Travel history tends to influence CL prevalence, implying that visits to endemic locations may provide possible exposure hazards. Home construction materials also have an impact on disease prevalence, with brick-built homes having lower CL rates than mud-built ones. The study emphasises repellent use's potential to reduce CL transmission, as indicated by a statistically significant difference in prevalence between repellent users and non-users. Furthermore, the presence of some animals near sick persons may have consequences, emphasising the need for increased domestic and wild animal surveillance.

References.

- Abuzaid, A. A., Abdoon, A. M., Aldahan, M. A., Alzahrani, A. G., Alhakeem, R. F., Asiri, A. M and Memish, Z. A. (2017). Cutaneous leishmaniasis in Saudi Arabia: a comprehensive overview. *Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases*, 17(10), 673-684.
- Ahmed, H., Khan, M., Rehman, H. U., Noor, H., Khan, N. A., Sheikh, M. A. K. J. A and Ahmad, W. (2019). Cutaneous leishmaniasis pattern: A Pakistani perspective. *J Entomol Zool*, 7(3), 868-73.
- Ahmed, T., Jadoon, S. S., Waqas, M., Ammar, M., Jian, L and Zhang, Q. (2021). Knowledge and Awareness about Leishmaniasis Disease in the General Public of Quetta, Pakistan. *Journal of Pharmacy Practice and Community Medicine*, 7(1).
- Alemayehu, B., & Alemayehu, M. (2017). Leishmaniasis: a review on parasite, vector and reservoir host. *Health Science Journal*, 11(4), 1.
- Al-Kamel, M. A. (2017). Stigmata in cutaneous leishmaniasis: Historical and new evidence-based concepts. *Our Dermatology Online*, 8(1), 81.
- Alvar J, Vélez ID, Bern C, et al. Leishmaniasis Worldwide and Global Estimates of Its Incidence. *PLoS ONE*. 2012;7(5): e35671.doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0035671
- Alvar, J., den Boer, M., & Dagne, D. A. (2021). Towards the elimination of visceral leishmaniasis as a public health problem in east Africa: reflections on an enhanced control strategy and a call for action. *The Lancet Global Health*, 9(12), e1763-e1769.

- Aronson, N. E and Joya, C. A. (2019). Cutaneous leishmaniasis: updates in diagnosis and management. *Infectious Disease Clinics*, 33(1), 101-117.
- Asfaram, S., Fakhar, M and Teshnizi, S. H. (2019). Is the cat an important reservoir host for visceral leishmaniasis? A systematic review with meta-analysis. *Journal of Venomous Animals and Toxins including Tropical Diseases*, 25.
- Ayaz, M. M., Nazir, M. M., Ullah, N., Zaman, A., Akbar, A., Zeeshan, M and Lindsay, D. S. (2018). Cutaneous leishmaniasis in the Metropolitan City of Multan, Pakistan, a neglected tropical disease. *Journal of medical entomology*, 55(4), 1040-1042.
- Azim, M., Khan, S. A., Ullah, S., Ullah, S and Anjum, S. I. (2021). Therapeutic advances in the topical treatment of cutaneous leishmaniasis: A review. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 15(3), e0009099.
- Bahrami, F., Harandi, A. M., & Rafati, S. (2018). Biomarkers of cutaneous leishmaniasis. *Frontiers in cellular and infection microbiology*, 8, 222.
- Bailey, F., Mondragon-Shem, K., Hotez, P., Ruiz-Postigo, J. A., Al-Salem, W., Acosta-Serrano, A and Molyneux, D. H. (2017). A new perspective on cutaneous leishmaniasis—Implications for global prevalence and burden of disease estimates. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*, 11(8), e0005739.
- Bamorovat, M., Sharifi, I., Aflatoonian, M. R., Karamoozian, A., Tahmouresi, A., Jafarzadeh, A and Barghi, M. (2022). Prophylactic effect of cutaneous leishmaniasis against COVID-19: a case-control field assessment. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 122, 155-161.
- Bashir, U., Tahir, M., Anwar, M. I and Manzoor, F. (2019). Comparison of Intralesional Meglumine Antimonite along with oral Itraconazole to Intralesional Meglumine Antimonite in the treatment of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 35(6), 1669.
- Bennis, Issam, et al. The mosquitoes that destroy your face. Social impact of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in South-eastern Morocco, A qualitative study. *PLoS One* 12.12 (2017): e0189906. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189906>
- Bi, K., Chen, Y., Zhao, S., Kuang, Y., & John Wu, C. H. (2018). Current visceral leishmaniasis research: a research review to inspire future study. *BioMed research international*, 2018.
- Brooker, Simon, et al. "Leishmaniasis in refugee and local Pakistani populations." *Emerging infectious diseases* 10.9 (2004): 1681. <https://doi.org/10.3201%2F1009.040179>

- Cantanhêde, L. M., Mata-Somarribas, C., Chourabi, K., Pereira da Silva, G., Dias das Chagas, B., de Oliveira R. Pereira, L and Cupolillo, E. (2021). The maze pathway of coevolution: A critical review over the Leishmania and its endosymbiotic history. *Genes*, 12(5), 657.
- Chahed, Mohamed Kouni, et al. "Psychological and psychosocial consequences of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis among women in Tunisia: preliminary findings from an exploratory study." *PLoS neglected tropical diseases* 10.10 (2016): e0005090. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0005090>
- Chapman, L. A., Dyson, L., Courtenay, O., Chowdhury, R., Bern, C., Medley, G. F and Hollingsworth, T. D. (2015). Quantification of the natural history of visceral leishmaniasis and consequences for control. *Parasites & vectors*, 8, 1-13.
- Damianou, A., Burge, R. J., Catta-Preta, C. M., Geoghegan, V., Nievas, Y. R., Newling, K and Mottram, J. C. (2020). Essential roles for deubiquitination in Leishmania life cycle progression. *PLoS Pathogens*, 16(6), e1008455.
- Detoni, M. B., Lima, D. M., Silva, T. P. D., Machado, L. F., Tomiotto-Pellissier, F., Costa, I. N and Melanda, F. N. (2019). Temporal and spatial distribution of American tegumentary leishmaniasis in north Paraná: 2010-2015. *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical*, 52.
- Du, R., Hotez, P. J., Al-Salem, W. S., & Acosta-Serrano, A. (2016). Old world cutaneous leishmaniasis and refugee crises in the Middle East and North Africa. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*, 10(5), e0004545.
- Efstathiou, A and Smirlis, D. (2021). Leishmania protein kinases: important regulators of the parasite life cycle and molecular targets for treating leishmaniasis. *Microorganisms*, 9(4), 691.
- Garza-Tovar, T. F., Sacriste-Hernández, M. I., Juárez-Durán, E. R and Arenas, R. (2020). An overview of the treatment of cutaneous leishmaniasis. *Faculty Reviews*, 9.
- Giri, S and Shaha, C. (2019). Leishmania donovani parasite requires Atg8 protein for infectivity and survival under stress. *Cell Death & Disease*, 10(11), 808.
- Gurel, M. S., Tekin, B and Uzun, S. (2020). Cutaneous leishmaniasis: A great imitator. *Clinics in dermatology*, 38(2), 140-151.
- Hussain, M., Munir, S., Khan, T. A., Khan, A., Ayaz, S., Jamal, M. A and Kasbari, M. (2018). Epidemiology of cutaneous leishmaniasis outbreak, Waziristan, Pakistan. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 24(1), 159.

- Iqbal, K. (2017). *Isolation, identification, evaluation and pharmacological effects of antileishmanial compounds* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Balochistan, Quetta).
- Jamal, Q., Shah, A., Rasheed, S. B and Adnan, M. (2020). In vitro Assessment and Characterization of the Growth and Life Cycle of *Leishmania tropica*. *Pakistan Journal of Zoology*, 52(2).
- Jewely, H. M and Zuhair, T. (2022). Evaluation of Antileishmanial Activity of *Osteospermum ecklonis* Extract of Aerial Parts against *Leishmania donovani*: in vitro (Conference Paper). *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences (P-ISSN 1683-3597 E-ISSN 2521-3512)*, 31(Suppl.), 45-53.
- Kayani, B., Sadiq, S., Rashid, H. B., Ahmed, N., Mahmood, A., Khaliq, M. S and Chaudhry, M. (2021). Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Pakistan: a neglected disease needing one health strategy. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 21, 1-10.
- Khan, K., Khan, N. H and Wahid, S. (2021). Systematic Review of Leishmaniasis in Pakistan: Evaluating Spatial Distribution and Risk Factors. *The Journal of Parasitology*, 107(4), 630-638.
- Khan, K., Wahid, S., Khan, N. H., Shah, S. U., Atta-Ur-Rahman, Sarwar, B and Ali, N. (2018). Geospatial and climatic patterns associated with the distribution of sand fly (Diptera: Psychodidae) vectors of leishmaniasis in Pakistan. *Journal of Medical Entomology*, 55(3), 626-633.
- Kohl, K., Zangger, H., Rossi, M., Isorce, N., Lye, L. F., Owens, K. L and Fasel, N. (2018). Importance of polyphosphate in the *Leishmania* life cycle. *Microbial cell*, 5(8), 371.
- Kumari, D., Tariq, H., Qadir, M. A., Imran, I., Farooq, G., Nasimullah, M and Meghwar, P. (2022). Incidence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Coastal Areas (Winder, Uthal and Lasbela) of Balochistan Pakistan. *Pak-Euro Journal of Medical and Life Sciences*, 5(2), 405-410.
- Luz, J. G. G., Carvalho, A. G. D., Naves, D. B., Dias, J. V. L and Fontes, C. J. F. (2019). Where, when, and how the diagnosis of human visceral leishmaniasis is defined: answers from the Brazilian control program. *Memórias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz*, 114.
- Mannan, S. B., Elhadad, H., Loc, T. T. H., Sadik, M., Mohamed, M. Y. F., Nam, N. H and Hamano, S. (2021). Prevalence and associated factors of asymptomatic leishmaniasis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Parasitology international*, 81, 102229.

- Meireles, C. B., Maia, L. C., Soares, G. C., Teodoro, I. P. P., Gadelha, M. D. S. V., da Silva, C. G. L. and de Lima, M. A. P. (2017). Atypical presentations of cutaneous leishmaniasis: a systematic review. *Acta Tropica*, 172, 240-254.
- Mhadhbi, M and Sassi, A. (2020). Infection of the equine population by *Leishmania* parasites. *Equine veterinary journal*, 52(1), 28-33.
- Mirzaei, A., Maleki, M., Masoumi, E and Maspi, N. (2021). A historical review of the role of cytokines involved in leishmaniasis. *Cytokine*, 145, 155297.
- Mokni, M. (2019). Cutaneous leishmaniasis. In *Annales de Dermatologie et de Venereologie* (Vol. 146, No. 3, pp. 232-246).
- Oliveira, Fabiano, et al. "Lesion size correlates with *Leishmania* antigen-stimulated TNF-levels in human cutaneous leishmaniasis." *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene* 85.1 (2011): 70. <https://doi.org/10.4269%2Fajtmh.2011.10-0680>
- Palma, D., Mercuriali, L., Figuerola, J., Montalvo, T., Bueno-Marí, R., Millet, J. P and Rius, C. (2021). Trends in the Epidemiology of Leishmaniasis in the City of Barcelona (1996–2019). *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 389.
- Qureshi, I., Solangi, M., Soomro, A., Baloch, W., Kumar, S and Khani, S. Q. (2019). Identification of cutaneous leishmaniasis in humans through polymerase chain reaction (pcr). *J. Adv. Parasitol*, 6(1), 7-11.
- Qurtas, D. S., & Shabila, N. P. (2020). Using Q-methodology to understand the perspectives and practical experiences of dermatologists about treatment difficulties of cutaneous leishmaniasis. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 20, 1-9.
- Rasheed, Z., Ahmed, A. A., Salem, T., Al-Dhubaibi, M. S., Al Robaee, A. A and Alzolibani, A. A. (2019). Prevalence of *Leishmania* species among patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis in Qassim province of Saudi Arabia. *BMC public health*, 19(1), 1-8.
- Saberi, R., Fakhar, M., Mohebali, M., Anvari, D and Gholami, S. (2019). Global status of synchronizing *Leishmania* RNA virus in *Leishmania* parasites: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *Transboundary and emerging diseases*, 66(6), 2244-2251.
- Santos, G. D. O., Jesus, N. P. S. D., Cerqueira-Braz, J. V., Santos, V. S and Lemos, L. M. D. D. (2019). Prevalence of HIV and associated factors among visceral leishmaniasis cases in an endemic area of Northeast Brazil. *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical*, 52.
- Sasidharan, S and Saudagar, P. (2021). Leishmaniasis: where are we and where are we heading? *Parasitology research*, 120, 1541-1554.

- Scott, P and Novais, F. O. (2016). Cutaneous leishmaniasis: immune responses in protection and pathogenesis. *Nature Reviews Immunology*, 16(9), 581-592.
- Sharquie, K. E and Jabbar, R. I. (2022). Leishmania Recidivans Could Be Induced by Intralesional Infiltration of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis by Sodium Stibogluconate, with New Therapeutic Trial. *Journal of Clinical & Experimental Investigations*, 13(1).
- Shita, E. Y., Semegn, E. N., Wubetu, G. Y., Abitew, A. M., Andualem, B. G and Alemneh, M. G. (2022). Prevalence of Leishmania RNA virus in Leishmania parasites in patients with tegumentary leishmaniasis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 16(6), e0010427.
- Steverding, D. (2017). The history of leishmaniasis. *Parasites & vectors*, 10(1), 1-10.
- Sunter, J and Gull, K. (2017). Shape, form, function and Leishmania pathogenicity: from textbook descriptions to biological understanding. *Open biology*, 7(9), 170165.
- Tahir, M., Bashir, U., Hafeez, J and Ghafoor, R. (2019). Safety and efficacy of miltefosine in cutaneous leishmaniasis: An open label, non-comparative study from Balochistan. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*, 35(2), 495.
- Ullah, N., Shah, M and Khan, M. S. (2020). A brief review on infestation of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Pakistan. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific & Technical Research*, 31(4), 24405-24408.
- Ullah, W., Yen, T. Y., Niaz, S., Nasreen, N., Tsai, Y. F., Rodriguez-Vivas, R. I and Tsai, K. H. (2023). Distribution and Risk of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 8(2), 128.
- Volpedo, G., Bhattacharya, P., Gannavaram, S., Pacheco-Fernandez, T., Oljuskin, T., Dey, R and Nakhasi, H. L. (2022). The history of live attenuated centrin gene-deleted leishmania vaccine candidates. *Pathogens*, 11(4), 431.

